

**PROBLEMS OF STUDENT PRACTICE IN HIGHER
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18281584>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 15th January 2026Accepted: 16th January 2026Online: 17th January 2026**KEYWORDS***student practice, higher
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The article examines the problems of organizing student practice in higher education institutions, its content, and effectiveness. The role of practice in linking theoretical knowledge with practical activity, developing students' professional competencies, and aligning education with labor market requirements is analyzed. Recommendations are provided for effective organization and assessment of practice, cooperation with employers, and the implementation of dual education elements.

Introduction. Today, one of the main requirements for higher education institutions in the global educational arena is the training of specialists with practical skills and professional competencies, who are competitive in the labor market. In achieving this goal, practical training and production practice that students receive during their studies are of particular importance. Because practice is an important means of consolidating theoretical knowledge, applying it in real working conditions, and forming readiness for future professional activity. At the same time, there are a number of systemic problems in the process of organizing and implementing student practice in higher education institutions, which lead to a decrease in the quality of education and insufficient formation of professional training of graduates. In particular, the main reasons for these problems are the fact that cooperation with internship bases remains formal, that internship programs do not fully meet the requirements of modern production and service industries, and that effective control and evaluation mechanisms over the internship process are not sufficiently established. Especially in the context of digitalization, innovative technologies, and rapid changes in the labor market, updating the content and forms of student internships is becoming an urgent task. During the internship, students are required to be treated not just as observers, but as subjects who can make independent decisions and actively participate in the work process. However, the formal conduct of internships, low student activity, and the fact that the results of internships remain at the level of paperwork sharply reduce the effectiveness of this process. In the context of reforms being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to reform the higher education system, strengthen the integration between education-production-employer, and introduce elements of dual education, the need to reconsider the content, organization mechanisms, and assessment system of student internships is increasing. This makes conducting scientific analyses on this topic, identifying existing problems and developing

solutions to them an urgent scientific and practical task. From this point of view, a comprehensive study of the problems encountered in student practice in higher education institutions, the development of scientifically based proposals and recommendations aimed at eliminating them is of great importance in improving the quality of education and training highly qualified personnel who meet the requirements of the labor market. The issues of organizing student practice, its content and effectiveness have been widely covered in numerous scientific studies in the field of higher education pedagogy, vocational education theory and educational management. An analysis of scientific literature shows that the problems of student practice are considered an urgent issue in the education systems of different countries, and various approaches have been developed to improve it [3]. In scientific sources devoted to the theory of pedagogy and vocational education (I.A. Zimnyaya, V.A. Slastyonin, N.V. Kuzmina and others), practice is interpreted as an integral part of the educational process, and its main task is to form professional competencies in students [1, 2]. In these studies, practice is assessed as an important stage that connects theoretical knowledge with practical activity. Some scientists (A.A. Verbitsky, Y.G. Tatur) paid attention to the issues of organizing practice based on contextual education and a competency-based approach, justifying the need to ensure the active participation of students in the practice process and bring them closer to the real professional environment [4, 5]. In their works, it was noted that the formal nature of practice has a negative impact on the preparation of graduates. In foreign studies (D. Kolb, J. Biggs, P. Ramsden), student practice is considered an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of education based on the theory of experiential learning [6, 7, 8]. In these studies, the formation of deep knowledge and skills through reflection, independent analysis and problem-solving in the process of practice is scientifically substantiated. In studies conducted from the point of view of the labor market and employer requirements (OECD, UNESCO materials), the gap between education and production is indicated as the main factor reducing the competitiveness of graduates [9, 10]. These sources suggest that dual education, strengthening industrial practice, and involving employers in the educational process are effective solutions. Studies conducted by Uzbek scientists also pay special attention to the issues of student practice. In particular, local studies noted the lack of cooperation with practice bases, the inconsistency of practice programs with modern requirements, and the formal nature of the assessment system as the main problems [11, 12, 13]. The need to increase student activity in the practice process and form professional motivation in them was also emphasized. An analysis of the literature shows that although some aspects of student practice are widely covered in existing studies, there is a need for a comprehensive analysis of the problems of its organization and the development of generalized scientific conclusions from the point of view of the integration of education and production. This study is significant in that it is aimed at filling this gap.

Practical recommendations developed based on the results of the study.

Practical recommendations developed based on the results of the study are aimed at improving the quality of organizing student internships in higher education institutions, bringing the educational process closer to the requirements of the labor market, and strengthening the integration between education and production. These recommendations were developed in the following main areas.

Recommendations aimed at improving the quality of organizing student internships.

1. In order to effectively organize student internships, it is first necessary to review internship programs and adapt them to the professional competencies of each educational area. During the internship, it is advisable to set specific tasks for students, not just as observers, but as active participants in the work process, enrich the content of the internship by giving independent assignments and analyzing their results. Also, clearly defining the responsibilities of internship leaders, developing methodological guidelines for them, and conducting systematic monitoring of students' activities during the internship will have a positive effect on the quality of internships.

2. Recommendations aimed at ensuring the competitiveness of graduates. Organizing student internships in accordance with the requirements of the labor market is an important factor in increasing the competitiveness of graduates. Therefore, during the internship, special attention should be paid to the formation of universal competencies such as communication skills, teamwork, independent decision-making and problem solving in students, along with professional knowledge. In addition, evaluating the results of internships with the participation of employers, early involvement of students in the production environment, and creating opportunities for subsequent employment for students who have shown themselves positively during internships will strengthen the position of graduates in the labor market.

3. Recommendations aimed at strengthening the integration of education and production. The study substantiated the need to establish close cooperation between educational institutions and production enterprises. In particular, the conclusion of long-term cooperation agreements with practice bases, the involvement of employers in the process of developing practice programs, and updating the content of practice based on their suggestions will ensure the integration of education and production. In addition, the gradual introduction of dual education elements into the practice process, the involvement of production specialists in the educational process, and the use of student practice results in solving real production problems will further strengthen this integration.

Conclusion. The practical recommendations developed based on the results of the study will serve to increase the effectiveness of organizing student practice, form professional competencies in graduates that meet the requirements of the labor market, and create an environment of stable cooperation between higher education institutions and production..

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